

Domain-general and stimulus-specific functional connectivity networks supporting working memory for faces, body parts, tools, and places

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Abstract

Working Memory (WM) load is a central WM characteristic that influences different task-dependent activities. Building on previous research, demonstrating that both WM load and visual stimulus category (faces, body parts, tools, and places) influence brain activity. This study focuses on differences in functional connectivity networks, using the network-based statistics (NBS) approach. For this purpose, we retrieved the WM functional MRI dataset from the Human Connectome Project dataset for 100 subjects. The results indicated that functional connectivity was predominantly negative under working memory load (0-back > 2-back) across all categories, with stronger connectivity observed within the Visual, Frontoparietal, and Dorsal Attention networks. Interestingly, the Default Mode Network also showed increased connectivity under greater working memory load, aligning with recent findings that suggest its involvement under higher working memory demands. These results demonstrate that there are both domain-general and stimulus-specific functional networks supporting working memory.

Keywords Working memory, fMRI, Functional Connectivity, Network Neuroscience, Network Based Statistic

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Data Availability

Published via [Impact Scholars](#), [original submission](#) and [development repositories](#).

Working memory (WM) is a core cognitive system responsible for the temporary maintenance and active manipulation of information, and it plays a functional role in supporting ongoing, goal-directed cognition (Baddeley & Hitch, 1994; Postle, 2006). WM is fundamental to a broad range of higher-order cognitive functions, such as language (Baddeley, 2003; Deldar *et al.*, 2021), learning (Sweller, 2020), planning (Ehrlich & Murray, 2022), reasoning, and fluid intelligence (Engle *et al.*, 1999; Smith & Osherson, 1995).

A central characteristic of WM concerns the amount of information that must be actively maintained to support task performance (i.e., WM load). Paradigms such as the n-back task (Barch *et al.*, 2013) are widely employed to systematically manipulate WM load and examine its effects on cognitive performance. WM load differentially modulates brain activation and connectivity. Low WM load (e.g., 0-back) is associated with predominantly right-lateralized activation, whereas higher load (e.g., 2-back) shows reduced functional connectivity (FC) and more bilateral engagement, involving fronto-parietal regions (Kim *et al.*, 2012).

Working memory is supported by both stimulus-specific and domain-general processes (Nozari & Martin, 2024). For example, brain activity was shown to be memory-load-dependent only during encoding, and the domain-general network was sensitive to load across encoding, maintenance, and retrieval (Li *et al.*, 2014). Recent work from (Assem *et al.*, 2025), using general linear modelling, shows that the prefrontal cortex contains a mixture of domain-general and stimulus-specific representations across stimulus categories (faces, body parts, tools, and places).

Recent studies using computational models examined differences between stimulus-selective brain regions for faces, places, bodies, and tools during working memory tasks. For example, visual working memory (VWM) of scenes and locations activated ventromedial visual stream regions in the parahippocampal scene area, medial and lateral parietal regions, and the medial orbitofrontal cortex (Rolls *et al.*, 2024). In the same model, face stimuli produced activations in regions in the ventrolateral fusiform face area, superior temporal sulcus (STS), inferior parietal visual, and somatosensory regions. With respect to motion and action-related stimuli (e.g., tools), even static visual stimuli can differentially engage broader functional networks during a working memory task. For example, objects like tools that imply motion and body-object interaction increased connectivity with motion-sensitive and sensorimotor cortical regions compared to stimuli that lack such affordances (e.g., scenes). In this same computational model, body parts stimuli rely on intermediate ventral stream area, visual motion regions, and somatosensory cortical regions (Rolls *et al.*, 2024).

Building on prior work demonstrating that both working memory load and stimulus category influence brain activity, the present study investigates the domain-general and stimulus-specific functional connectivity networks that support WM across different stimulus types. We hypothesize that the working memory network varies as a function of stimulus category, owing to the unique regions utilized for perception across these stimulus types. The flexibility of the working memory network to adapt to better support the specific regions involved in the perception of distinct stimuli would be consistent with recent WM computational modelling research (Rolls *et al.*, 2024) as well as semantic memory research demonstrating unique access to the semantic memory network depending on the prime stimulus type during reading (Neudorf *et al.*, 2019a; 2019b). To test this hypothesis, we compare functional connectivity matrices between WM-load (0-back and 2-back) and compare these WM load connectivity matrices between visual stimulus types (faces, body parts, tools, and places) by applying the network-based statistic to data from the Human Connectome Project (Van Essen *et al.*, 2013).

We used task-MRI data for the Working Memory N-back Task (Barch et al., 2013) from the Human Connectome Project - Young Adult 2025 Release 100 Unrelated Subjects (Van Essen et al., 2013). Participants included 100 adults ($F = 54$) with mean age $M = 29.35$, $SD = 3.52$.

Each run had 8 task blocks (10 trials \times 2.5 s) and 4 fixation blocks (4 \times 15 s). Task blocks alternated between 2-back (respond if stimulus matches 2 trials back) and 0-back (respond to a presented target). Stimuli (faces, body parts, tools, places) were presented in separate blocks. Full acquisition and preprocessing pipeline details are available in this original publication. fMRI task data were preprocessed using the HCP Minimal Preprocessing Pipelines (MPP) to maximize anatomical alignment, reduce structured noise, and preserve neural signal fidelity across participants. Initial preprocessing included the Generic fMRI Volume Processing Pipeline, which performs gradient distortion correction, motion correction, EPI distortion correction, spatial normalization, and registration to structural images. Followed by the Generic fMRI Surface Processing Pipeline, which maps cortical data onto standardized cortical surfaces to improve cross-subject anatomical correspondence and reduce partial-volume effects. The MSMAll pipeline was subsequently applied to align cortical features across subjects within CIFTI grayordinate space using multimodal information, thereby improving functional correspondence beyond conventional anatomical registration. Noise reduction procedures included multi-run FIX, an ICA-based automated denoising framework that identifies and removes non-neuronal artifacts such as motion, physiological noise, and scanner-related components across concatenated runs. Updated 2025–2026 HCP processing procedures further incorporated Reclean combined with spatial ICA (sICA), in which ICA components were reclassified after an additional cleaning step to improve separation of neural and artifactual signals, followed by Reclean with temporal ICA (tICA) to selectively remove temporally structured global and physiological noise while minimizing loss of neural variance. Additional preprocessing refinements included spin-echo based (SEBASED) intensity bias field correction to improve spatial homogeneity of fMRI signal intensity across the brain. Consistent with recent HCP recommendations, explicit regression of motion parameters was omitted from the final cleaning stages because ICA-based denoising approaches were considered sufficient for artifact removal and helped avoid unnecessary suppression of true neural signal. All processed data were represented in standardized CIFTI grayordinate space to support anatomically and functionally aligned group-level analyses.

We performed time-domain normalization using the `hcp_utils.normalize` function from the `hcp_utils` library (<https://rmldj.github.io/hcp-utils/>). This was done so that each voxel has a zero temporal mean and unit standard deviation. Parcellation was performed using the Multi-Modal Parcellation (MMP 1.0) (Glasser et al., 2016), which partitioned each hemisphere of the cortex into 180 parcels (360 in total) by taking the mean over each parcel. Additionally, we have added 18 subcortical regions, with subcortical labels derived from the Cole-Anticevic Brain-wide Network Partition (Ji et al., 2019). Cortical regions were further assigned to functional networks using the Yeo 7-network parcellation (Yeo et al., 2011).

Following parcellation, data were organized per subject across two Working Memory (WM) task runs. Further, two parcellated time series were filtered by using a 5th-order zero-phase Butterworth bandpass filter (0.01–0.1 Hz), see (Hallquist et al., 2013), implemented via second-order sections (SOS) with forward-backward filtering to ensure zero phase distortion, using the SciPy signal processing library (`scipy.signal.butter` and `scipy.signal.sosfiltfilt`), see (Virtanen et al., 2020). Following parcellation, Pearson correlations between regional time series were computed to construct functional connectivity matrices, which were subsequently Fisher Z-transformed to normalize the distribution of correlation coefficients prior to NBS analysis.

Task epochs were extracted for 0-back and 2-back conditions across four stimulus categories (faces, body parts, tools, places), yielding 8 conditions in total. Since our functional connectivity analyses operated directly on BOLD time series without HRF convolution, the hemodynamic delay must be accounted for explicitly. The time series was therefore shifted by 8 TRs (= 5.76 s), corresponding to the expected peak of the grey matter hemodynamic response function ($\sim 6.14 \pm 0.27$ s), see (Li et al., 2019), ensuring that connectivity analyses reflect peak neural activity rather than the rising phase of the hemodynamic response. Therefore, event onsets were shifted by 8 TRs (≈ 5.76 s) to account for hemodynamic response delay, and there were 39 TRs per condition per run. Epochs of the same condition were subsequently concatenated across runs, yielding 78 TRs per condition. Functional connectivity (FC) matrices were computed by calculating the Pearson correlation between parcels, yielding one symmetric 378×378 FC matrix per condition per subject.

The network-based statistic (NBS) is a connectome-level inferential method used to identify a subnetwork whose connectivity differs between conditions (Zalesky et al., 2010). This method performs an edge-wise t-test across all connections, applies a primary threshold to isolate suprathreshold edges, identifies the connected components among the edges, and then uses permutation testing to determine if the size of the subnetwork exceeds what would be expected by chance (Nichols & Holmes, 2002). WM load effects (2-back vs. 0-back) were assessed for each stimulus category using NBS, with 1,000 permutations and a t-statistic threshold of $t = 5.217$ ($p < 0.00001$, $df = 99$). All identified components survived the permutation-based family-wise error (FWE) correction and were statistically significant at $p < 0.001$ (minimum achievable p-value given 1000 permutations), indicating that no permutation exceeded the observed test statistic.

NBS was applied separately for each of the four task categories to identify functional connections that significantly exceeded baseline. This yielded four category-specific connection sets, each containing only NBS-surviving connections. Domain-general (shared) connections were then identified as those present in all four NBS-thresholded connection sets simultaneously. Finally, category-specific unique connections were derived by removing the shared connections from each category's NBS connection set, retaining only those connections that were significant in that category but not common to all four categories. This resulted in two types of connection sets: one shared set representing domain-general connectivity, and four unique sets each reflecting connectivity specific to a single task category.

The circular plots in [Figure 1A - D](#) displays two connection types: shared (domain-general) connections representing the intersection of significant edges across all four category-specific NBS results, and category-specific unique connections representing edges significant within a given stimulus category but absent from the shared set. Across all categories, we observed unique stimulus-dependent connectivity that was predominantly negative ([Figure 1A - D](#)). The Face condition showed the highest number of unique connections ($n = 2566$), followed by Body ($n = 2321$), Tools ($n = 1104$), and Places ($n = 933$). Negative edges dominated in every category, comprising from 80.3% to 89.6% of connections, with Body and Places showing the strongest skew toward negative connectivity. The domain-general analysis ([Figure 1E](#)) revealed shared connections, all except one of which were negative, indicating a highly consistent reduction in connectivity across all task conditions with the increase of WM load. [Figure 1F](#) demonstrates aggregated connectivity strength within each network was normalized by the number of constituent regions to account for differences in network size, yielding a size-independent measure of connectivity strength. These connections were primarily concentrated within frontoparietal and dorsal-

attention networks (see Figure 1F), representing a significant domain-general network underlying visual working memory load.

Figure 1: Network-based statistic (NBS) connectivity results across the four stimulus categories. Panels A–D show circular connectivity plots for each category: Face (A), Body (B), Tools (C), and Places (D). Nodes are ordered by hemisphere and functional network, with node colors indicating network membership. Edges represent suprathreshold connections identified by the NBS analysis, with warm (orange) and cool (purple) colors indicating positive and negative effects, respectively. Panel E shows the connectivity pattern common across the four categories, highlighting edges consistently shared between conditions. Panel F shows the network-level total activation summary across categories, displaying the normalized aggregated connectivity strength for each network for all four categories. The ordered node labels are given in Supplementary Table 6.

Among the stimulus-dependent unique networks, negative connections (0-back > 2-back) are prominent and involve Visual (I and II), Frontoparietal, Posterior Multimodal, and Dorsal Attention networks, but utilize unique connections and regions to support this inter-network communication. Supplementary Tables 1–4 present detailed inter-regional functional connectivity, emphasizing unique connection patterns within each network. Representative examples from these tables include category-specific connectivity for faces (fusiform gyrus), body parts (inferior frontal sulcus), tools (left parahippocampal

cortex), and places (ventromedial and parahippocampal regions). Supplementary Table 5 presents the shared functional connections associated with the domain-general network.

In line with our hypothesis, unique connections were broadly consistent with expected category-specific patterns (e.g., face-related connectivity in the fusiform gyrus). Further, positive functional connections (2-back > 0-back) were relatively sparse and weaker in magnitude. When present, they primarily involved regions within the visual, dorsal attention, and frontoparietal networks, with additional recruitment of the default mode network, an observation of interest given its reported involvement under higher working memory load (Vatansever *et al.*, 2015). Shared, domain-general connections were predominantly negative (0-back > 2-back) and showed higher connectivity in visual, frontoparietal, and dorsal attention networks.

To complement our findings, future studies could benefit from integrating alternative analytical approaches. For example, multivariate connectome methods (MCM) like partial least squares (PLS) offer a way to analyze global patterns of connectivity across all edges simultaneously. These approaches are well-suited for capturing distributed effects. Similarly, multivoxel pattern analysis (MVPA) could identify representational patterns of activation that distinguish stimulus types during a WM task. This method could be used to build on the univariate approaches used recently to compare WM activation between stimulus types (Assem *et al.*, 2025). Together, these complementary approaches can provide a more comprehensive characterization of domain-general and stimulus-specific working memory brain networks.

A potential limitation of the present study is the relatively short epoch length per stimulus category ($78 \text{ TRs} \times 0.72 \text{ s} \approx 56 \text{ s}$), which may affect the reliability of functional connectivity estimates. Although NBS was applied with a stringent threshold and permutation-based FWE correction to mitigate spurious connections, future studies employing longer task epochs or larger sample sizes would help to further validate the stability of the reported category-specific connectivity patterns.

In conclusion, we have demonstrated that WM relies not only on a domain-general network, but also stimulus-specific subnetworks tailored to the specific regions relied on for the perceptual processing of the stimulus. Our analysis showed specialized, category-specific processing for faces (fusiform gyrus), body parts (inferior frontal sulcus), tools (left parahippocampal cortex), and places (ventromedial and parahippocampal regions). Together, these findings highlight a specialized neural organization that supports working memory of different types of visual information.

1. SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

1.a. Supplementary Table S1

Rank	Region 1	Network 1	Region 2	Network 2	Direction	t-value	t
1	Left Visual Area 3CD	Visual2	Right Anterior Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-14.547	14.547
2	Left Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Right Intraparietal 2	Frontoparietal	Negative	-13.995	13.995
3	Left Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Right Area p9-46v	Frontoparietal	Negative	-12.298	12.298
4	Left Visual Area 3CD	Visual2	Right Intraparietal 2	Frontoparietal	Negative	-11.867	11.867
5	Right Anterior Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Right Visual Area 3CD	Visual2	Negative	-11.351	11.351
6	Left Lateral Intraparietal Dorsal	Dorsal-attention	Right Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Negative	-11.172	11.172
7	Left Parahippocampal	Visual2	Right Anterior Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-11.092	11.092
8	Left Visual Area 4	Visual2	Right Anterior Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-11.078	11.078
9	Right Visual Area 4	Visual2	Right Lateral Intraparietal Dorsal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-10.984	10.984
10	Left Parahippocampal	Visual2	Right Fusiform Face Complex	Visual2	Negative	-10.972	10.972
11	Left Intraparietal 2	Frontoparietal	Right Visual Area 3CD	Visual2	Negative	-10.934	10.934
12	Left Visual Area 4 Transitional	Visual2	Right Visual Area 4	Visual2	Negative	-10.872	10.872
13	Left Visual Area 3B	Visual2	Right Intraparietal 1	Frontoparietal	Negative	-10.775	10.775
14	Left Intraparietal 2	Frontoparietal	Right Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Negative	-10.765	10.765
15	Left Lateral Intraparietal Dorsal	Dorsal-attention	Left Parahippocampal	Visual2	Negative	-10.750	10.750
16	Right Intraparietal 2	Frontoparietal	Right Visual Area 3CD	Visual2	Negative	-10.702	10.702
17	Left Posterior Inferotemporal	Visual2	Right Parahippocampal	Visual2	Negative	-10.699	10.699
18	Right Lateral Intraparietal Dorsal	Dorsal-attention	Right Visual Area 3CD	Visual2	Negative	-10.678	10.678
19	Left Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	R_i6-8	Frontoparietal	Negative	-10.677	10.677
20	Left Posterior Inferotemporal	Visual2	Left Parahippocampal	Visual2	Negative	-10.624	10.624
21	Left Primary Visual Cortex	Visual1	Right Anterior Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-10.623	10.623
22	Left Parahippocampal	Visual2	Right Lateral Intraparietal Dorsal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-10.588	10.588
23	Left Lateral Intraparietal Dorsal	Dorsal-attention	Left Visual Area 3CD	Visual2	Negative	-10.558	10.558
24	Left Area p9-46v	Frontoparietal	Right Visual Area 3CD	Visual2	Negative	-10.546	10.546
25	Left Fusiform Face Complex	Visual2	Left Parahippocampal	Visual2	Negative	-10.518	10.518
26	Left Parahippocampal	Visual2	Right Posterior Inferotemporal	Visual2	Negative	-10.505	10.505
27	Left Intraparietal 1	Frontoparietal	Right Primary Visual Cortex	Visual1	Negative	-10.483	10.483
28	Right Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Right Area 8C	Frontoparietal	Negative	-10.448	10.448
29	Right Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	R_i6-8	Frontoparietal	Negative	-10.416	10.416
30	Left Intraparietal 2	Frontoparietal	Left Visual Area 3CD	Visual2	Negative	-10.415	10.415
31	Left Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Right Premotor 6a	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-10.392	10.392
32	Left Parahippocampal	Visual2	Right Medial Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-10.312	10.312
33	Left Intraparietal 2	Frontoparietal	Right Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-10.302	10.302
34	Left Visual Area 4	Visual2	Left Parahippocampal	Visual2	Negative	-10.295	10.295
35	Right Intraparietal 1	Frontoparietal	Right Visual Area 3CD	Visual2	Negative	-10.288	10.288
36	Left Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Left Premotor 6a	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-10.287	10.287
37	Left Primary Visual Cortex	Visual1	Left Intraparietal 2	Frontoparietal	Negative	-10.264	10.264
38	Left Visual Area 3B	Visual2	Left Area 7 Posterior Medial	Frontoparietal	Negative	-10.253	10.253
39	Left Area 7 Posterior Medial	Frontoparietal	Right Secondary Visual Cortex	Visual2	Negative	-10.231	10.231
40	Left Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Right Intraparietal 1	Frontoparietal	Negative	-10.212	10.212

41	Left Area 7 Posterior Medial	Frontoparietal	Right Dorsal Visual Temporal	Visual1	Negative	-10.145	10.145
42	Left Visual Area 4 Transitional	Visual2	Right Primary Visual Cortex	Visual1	Negative	-10.135	10.135
43	Right Visual Area 4	Visual2	Right Anterior Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-10.125	10.125
44	Left Intraparietal 1	Frontoparietal	Right Visual Area 3CD	Visual2	Negative	-10.123	10.123
45	Left Visual Area 3CD	Visual2	Right Intraparietal 1	Frontoparietal	Negative	-10.092	10.092
46	Left Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Right Prefrontal Medial	Frontoparietal	Negative	-9.987	9.987
47	Left Area 7 Posterior Medial	Frontoparietal	Right Visual Area 3A	Visual2	Negative	-9.969	9.969
48	Left Area p9-46v	Frontoparietal	Left Visual Area 3CD	Visual2	Negative	-9.960	9.960
49	Left Visual Area 4	Visual2	Right Lateral Intraparietal Dorsal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-9.929	9.929
50	Left Area p9-46v	Frontoparietal	Right Visual Area 3	Visual2	Negative	-9.865	9.865

Table 1: Top 50 unique functional network connections for faces.

1.b. Supplementary Table S2

Rank	Region 1	Network 1	Region 2	Network 2	Direction	t-value	t
1	Left Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Right Area p9-46v	Frontoparietal	Negative	-14.132	14.132
2	Right Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	R_i6-8	Frontoparietal	Negative	-14.055	14.055
3	Left Medial Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Left Posterior Gyrus Parietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-13.230	13.230
4	Left Anterior Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Right Posterior Gyrus Parietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-12.744	12.744
5	Left Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	R_i6-8	Frontoparietal	Negative	-12.664	12.664
6	Left Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Right Intraparietal 1	Frontoparietal	Negative	-12.651	12.651
7	Right Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Right Intraparietal 1	Frontoparietal	Negative	-12.589	12.589
8	Right Dorsal Visual Temporal	Visual1	Right Intraparietal 2	Frontoparietal	Negative	-12.398	12.398
9	Left Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Right Intraparietal 2	Frontoparietal	Negative	-12.332	12.332
10	Left Intraparietal 1	Frontoparietal	Right Intraparietal 1	Frontoparietal	Negative	-12.248	12.248
11	Left Lateral Intraparietal Dorsal	Dorsal-attention	Left Posterior Gyrus Parietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-12.196	12.196
12	Left Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Right Intraparietal 1	Frontoparietal	Negative	-12.050	12.050
13	Left Posterior Gyrus Parietal	Dorsal-attention	Right Anterior Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-12.048	12.048
14	Left Visual Area 3B	Visual2	Right Intraparietal 2	Frontoparietal	Negative	-12.029	12.029
15	Left Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Right Area p9-46v	Frontoparietal	Negative	-11.989	11.989
16	Left Visual Area 3CD	Visual2	Right Anterior Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-11.818	11.818
17	Right Visual Area 3B	Visual2	Right Lateral Intraparietal Dorsal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-11.790	11.790
18	Left Posterior Gyrus Parietal	Dorsal-attention	Right Medial Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-11.756	11.756
19	Left Lateral Intraparietal Dorsal	Dorsal-attention	Right Medial Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-11.750	11.750
20	Right Anterior Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Right Visual Area 3CD	Visual2	Negative	-11.696	11.696
21	Left Dorsal Visual Temporal	Visual1	Right Intraparietal 2	Frontoparietal	Negative	-11.610	11.610
22	Left Anterior Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Right Dorsal Visual Temporal	Visual1	Negative	-11.605	11.605
23	Right Inferior Frontal Junction Posterior	Frontoparietal	Right Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-11.484	11.484
24	Left Intraparietal 2	Frontoparietal	Right Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-11.446	11.446
25	Left Parahippocampal	Visual2	Right Posterior Gyrus Parietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-11.388	11.388
26	Left Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	L_i6-8	Frontoparietal	Negative	-11.275	11.275
27	Left Lateral Intraparietal Dorsal	Dorsal-attention	Right Posterior Gyrus Parietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-11.273	11.273
28	Left Intraparietal 1	Frontoparietal	Right Area p9-46v	Frontoparietal	Negative	-11.235	11.235

29	Right Premotor 6a	Dorsal-attention	Right Dorsal Visual Temporal	Visual1	Negative	-11.215	11.215
30	Left Dorsal Visual Temporal	Visual1	Right Area p9-46v	Frontoparietal	Negative	-11.186	11.186
31	Left Medial Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Right Inferior Frontal Sulcus Posterior	Frontoparietal	Negative	-11.169	11.169
32	Left Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Right Inferior Frontal Sulcus Posterior	Frontoparietal	Negative	-11.164	11.164
33	Left Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Right Intraparietal 2	Frontoparietal	Negative	-11.130	11.130
34	Left Intraparietal 1	Frontoparietal	Left Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-11.119	11.119
35	Left Inferior Frontal Junction Posterior	Frontoparietal	Right Medial Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-11.099	11.099
36	Right Area p9-46v	Frontoparietal	Right Dorsal Visual Temporal	Visual1	Negative	-10.994	10.994
37	Left Intraparietal Sulcus 1	Visual2	Right Lateral Intraparietal Dorsal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-10.982	10.982
38	Left Inferior Frontal Sulcus Anterior	Frontoparietal	Right Medial Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-10.888	10.888
39	Left Parahippocampal	Visual2	Right Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-10.877	10.877
40	Left Posterior Gyrus Parietal	Dorsal-attention	Right Lateral Intraparietal Dorsal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-10.858	10.858
41	Left Intraparietal 1	Frontoparietal	Right Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-10.857	10.857
42	Left Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Right Area 8C	Frontoparietal	Negative	-10.760	10.760
43	Left Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Right Inferior Frontal Junction Posterior	Frontoparietal	Negative	-10.695	10.695
44	Right Intraparietal 2	Frontoparietal	Right Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-10.690	10.690
45	Right Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Right Prefrontal Medial	Frontoparietal	Negative	-10.665	10.665
46	Left Intraparietal 1	Frontoparietal	Right Lateral Intraparietal Dorsal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-10.657	10.657
47	Right Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Right Area 8C	Frontoparietal	Negative	-10.640	10.640
48	Left Medial Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Right Intraparietal 1	Frontoparietal	Negative	-10.595	10.595
49	Left Posterior Gyrus Parietal	Dorsal-attention	Left Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-10.550	10.550
50	Right Medial Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Right Inferior Frontal Sulcus Posterior	Frontoparietal	Negative	-10.548	10.548

Table 2: Top 50 unique functional network connections for bodies.

1.c. Supplementary Table S3

Rank	Region 1	Network 1	Region 2	Network 2	Direction	t-value	t
1	Left Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	L_i6-8	Frontoparietal	Negative	-12.250	12.250
2	Left Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Right Area p9-46v	Frontoparietal	Negative	-11.969	11.969
3	Right Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	R_i6-8	Frontoparietal	Negative	-11.927	11.927
4	Left Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	R_i6-8	Frontoparietal	Negative	-11.509	11.509
5	Left Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Right Intraparietal 2	Frontoparietal	Negative	-10.516	10.516
6	Left Intraparietal 2	Frontoparietal	Right Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Negative	-10.422	10.422
7	L_i6-8	Frontoparietal	Right Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Negative	-10.302	10.302
8	Left Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Left Area 8C	Frontoparietal	Negative	-10.284	10.284
9	Left Area 8C	Frontoparietal	Right Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Negative	-10.169	10.169
10	Left Intraparietal 2	Frontoparietal	Right Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-10.143	10.143
11	Left Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Right Visual Area 3	Visual2	Negative	-10.067	10.067
12	Left Primary Visual Cortex	Visual1	Left Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-9.866	9.866
13	Right Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Right Intraparietal 1	Frontoparietal	Negative	-9.678	9.678
14	Left Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Right Intraparietal 1	Frontoparietal	Negative	-9.354	9.354

15	Left Retrosplenial Cortex	Frontoparietal	R_i6-8	Frontoparietal	Negative	-9.305	9.305
16	Left Intraparietal Sulcus 1	Visual2	Right Visual Area 3	Visual2	Negative	-9.198	9.198
17	Left Area 8C	Frontoparietal	Right Retrosplenial Cortex	Frontoparietal	Negative	-9.162	9.162
18	Left Intraparietal 1	Frontoparietal	Right Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-8.975	8.975
19	Left Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Left Area 9 Medial	Default	Positive	8.946	8.946
20	Left Retrosplenial Cortex	Frontoparietal	L_i6-8	Frontoparietal	Negative	-8.848	8.848
21	Right Visual Area 8	Visual2	Right Ventromedial V3	Visual2	Negative	-8.829	8.829
22	Left Primary Visual Cortex	Visual1	Right Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-8.816	8.816
23	Right Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Right Area 8BM	Frontoparietal	Negative	-8.781	8.781
24	Left Intraparietal 1	Frontoparietal	Right Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Negative	-8.764	8.764
25	Left Ventromedial V3	Visual2	Right Visual Area 3CD	Visual2	Negative	-8.749	8.749
26	Left Somatosensory 3b	Somatomotor	Left Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Positive	8.710	8.710
27	Left Visual Area 3B	Visual2	Left Ventromedial V3	Visual2	Negative	-8.665	8.665
28	Left Intraparietal 1	Frontoparietal	Right Intraparietal 1	Frontoparietal	Negative	-8.623	8.623
29	Left Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Left Lateral Intraparietal Dorsal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-8.542	8.542
30	Left Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Right Secondary Visual Cortex	Visual2	Negative	-8.540	8.540
31	Right Retrosplenial Cortex	Frontoparietal	Right Intraparietal 2	Frontoparietal	Negative	-8.495	8.495
32	Right Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Right Lateral Intraparietal Dorsal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-8.446	8.446
33	Left Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Right Area 8BM	Frontoparietal	Negative	-8.426	8.426
34	Left Visual Area 3B	Visual2	Right Visual Area 8	Visual2	Negative	-8.425	8.425
35	Right Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Right Area 8C	Frontoparietal	Negative	-8.414	8.414
36	Left Ventral Visual Complex	Visual2	Right Visual Area 8	Visual2	Negative	-8.407	8.407
37	Left Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Right Area 8C	Frontoparietal	Negative	-8.404	8.404
38	Left Retrosplenial Cortex	Frontoparietal	Right Area p9-46v	Frontoparietal	Negative	-8.391	8.391
39	Left Visual Area 3B	Visual2	Right Ventromedial V3	Visual2	Negative	-8.388	8.388
40	Left Visual Area 3CD	Visual2	Right Visual Area 3CD	Visual2	Negative	-8.299	8.299
41	Left Area 9 Medial	Default	Right Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Positive	8.273	8.273
42	Right Primary Visual Cortex	Visual1	Right Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Negative	-8.270	8.270
43	Left Visual Area 4	Visual2	Left Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-8.239	8.239
44	Left Primary Visual Cortex	Visual1	Right Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Negative	-8.229	8.229
45	Left Inferior Frontal Junction Posterior	Frontoparietal	Left Anterior Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-8.203	8.203
46	Left Area p9-46v	Frontoparietal	Right Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-8.195	8.195
47	Left Primary Somatosensory	Somatomotor	Right Visual Area 4 Transitional	Visual2	Negative	-8.164	8.164
48	Left Visual Area 4	Visual2	Right Visual Area 3B	Visual2	Negative	-8.126	8.126
49	Left Visual Area 4	Visual2	Left Visual Area 3CD	Visual2	Negative	-8.121	8.121
50	Left Visual Area 3	Visual2	Left Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-8.118	8.118

Table 3: Top 50 unique functional network connections for places.

1.d. Supplementary Table S4

Rank	Region 1	Network 1	Region 2	Network 2	Direction	t-value	t
1	Left Parahippocampal	Visual2	Right Medial Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-11.875	11.875
2	Right Medial Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Right Parahippocampal	Visual2	Negative	-10.512	10.512
3	Left Area 7 Parietal Lobule	Dorsal-attention	Left Parahippocampal	Visual2	Negative	-9.991	9.991

4	Left Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Right Lateral Intraparietal Ventral	Visual2	Negative	-9.539	9.539
5	Left Visual Area 4	Visual2	Right Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-9.513	9.513
6	Left Primary Visual Cortex	Visual1	Left Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-9.436	9.436
7	Left Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Right Parahippocampal	Visual2	Negative	-9.362	9.362
8	Left Parahippocampal	Visual2	Right Area 7 Parietal Lobule	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-9.311	9.311
9	Left Inferior Frontal Junction Posterior	Frontoparietal	Right Inferior Frontal Junction Posterior	Frontoparietal	Negative	-9.197	9.197
10	Left Parahippocampal	Visual2	Right Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-9.134	9.134
11	Right Visual Area 3B	Visual2	Right Lateral Intraparietal Ventral	Visual2	Negative	-9.128	9.128
12	Left Primary Visual Cortex	Visual1	Right Visual Area 3B	Visual2	Negative	-9.119	9.119
13	Left Parahippocampal	Visual2	Left Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-9.115	9.115
14	Left Primary Visual Cortex	Visual1	Right Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-8.859	8.859
15	Left Area 7 Parietal Lobule	Dorsal-attention	Right Parahippocampal	Visual2	Negative	-8.752	8.752
16	Right Visual Area 4	Visual2	Right Intraparietal Sulcus 1	Visual2	Negative	-8.729	8.729
17	Left Visual Area 3B	Visual2	Right Intraparietal Sulcus 1	Visual2	Negative	-8.726	8.726
18	Left Primary Visual Cortex	Visual1	Right Lateral Intraparietal Ventral	Visual2	Negative	-8.707	8.707
19	Right Primary Visual Cortex	Visual1	Right Lateral Intraparietal Ventral	Visual2	Negative	-8.444	8.444
20	Left Parahippocampal	Visual2	Right Posterior Gyrus Parietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-8.390	8.390
21	Right Intraparietal Sulcus 1	Visual2	Right Parahippocampal	Visual2	Negative	-8.383	8.383
22	Left Visual Area 4	Visual2	Right Intraparietal Sulcus 1	Visual2	Negative	-8.367	8.367
23	Left Primary Visual Cortex	Visual1	Right Parietal Eye Field	Cingulo-Opercular	Negative	-8.347	8.347
24	Left Primary Visual Cortex	Visual1	Right Primary Visual Cortex	Visual1	Negative	-8.343	8.343
25	Left Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Right Inferior Frontal Junction Posterior	Frontoparietal	Negative	-8.331	8.331
26	Right Parahippocampal	Visual2	Right Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-8.298	8.298
27	Left Primary Visual Cortex	Visual1	Left Intraparietal Sulcus 1	Visual2	Negative	-8.250	8.250
28	Left Intraparietal Sulcus 1	Visual2	Right Lateral Intraparietal Ventral	Visual2	Negative	-8.240	8.240
29	Left Inferior Frontal Junction Posterior	Frontoparietal	Left Parahippocampal	Visual2	Negative	-8.202	8.202
30	Left Parahippocampal	Visual2	Right Inferior Frontal Junction Posterior	Frontoparietal	Negative	-8.184	8.184
31	Left Visual Area 4	Visual2	Left Medial Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-8.157	8.157
32	Left Area 7 Parietal Lobule	Dorsal-attention	Right Lateral Occipital 3	Visual2	Negative	-8.157	8.157
33	Left Visual Area 4	Visual2	Right Lateral Intraparietal Dorsal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-8.155	8.155
34	Left Intraparietal Sulcus 1	Visual2	Left Visual Area 3B	Visual2	Negative	-8.141	8.141
35	Left Parahippocampal	Visual2	Right Lateral Intraparietal Dorsal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-8.120	8.120
36	Left Visual Area 4	Visual2	Left Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-8.112	8.112
37	Right Area 7 Parietal Lobule	Dorsal-attention	Right Parahippocampal	Visual2	Negative	-8.087	8.087
38	Left Parahippocampal	Visual2	Right Anterior Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-8.085	8.085
39	Left Area 7 Parietal Lobule	Dorsal-attention	Right Lateral Intraparietal Ventral	Visual2	Negative	-8.067	8.067
40	Right Visual Area 3B	Visual2	Right Parahippocampal	Visual2	Negative	-8.062	8.062
41	Right Lateral Occipital 1	Visual2	Right Medial Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-8.055	8.055
42	Left Visual Area 3B	Visual2	Right Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-8.020	8.020
43	Left Inferior Frontal Junction Posterior	Frontoparietal	Right Intraparietal Sulcus 1	Visual2	Negative	-7.988	7.988
44	Left Visual Area 7	Visual2	Right Medial Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-7.972	7.972

45	Left Visual Area 3	Visual2	Left Medial Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-7.967	7.967
46	Left Visual Area 4	Visual2	Right Visual Area 3B	Visual2	Negative	-7.965	7.965
47	Left Anterior Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Right Visual Area 3A	Visual2	Negative	-7.950	7.950
48	Left Visual Area 7	Visual2	Left Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-7.917	7.917
49	Right Visual Area 3B	Visual2	Right Lateral Intraparietal Dorsal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-7.905	7.905
50	Left Area 7 Posterior Medial	Frontoparietal	Right Visual Area 3A	Visual2	Negative	-7.882	7.882

Table 4: Top 50 unique functional network connections for tools.

1.e. Supplementary Table S5

Rank	Region 1	Network 1	Region 2	Network 2	Direction	Common t-value	Common t	t (Face)	t (Body)	t (Places)	t (Tools)
1	Right Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Right Intraparietal 2	Frontoparietal	Negative	-11.211	11.211	-14.721	-12.232	-11.922	-5.971
2	Right Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Right Area p9-46v	Frontoparietal	Negative	-11.194	11.194	-12.785	-14.269	-11.837	-5.886
3	Left Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Right Medial Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-10.937	10.937	-10.715	-12.764	-9.843	-10.425
4	Right Medial Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Right Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-10.931	10.931	-12.863	-13.285	-8.510	-9.065
5	Left Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Left Area p9-46v	Frontoparietal	Negative	-10.726	10.726	-12.797	-12.582	-11.324	-6.202
6	Right Lateral Intraparietal Dorsal	Dorsal-attention	Right Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-10.565	10.565	-14.014	-13.061	-7.991	-7.194
7	Left Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Right Area 7 Posterior Medial	Frontoparietal	Negative	-10.524	10.524	-11.755	-13.351	-11.583	-5.405
8	Left Medial Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Right Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-10.437	10.437	-10.645	-12.860	-10.208	-8.035
9	Left Area p9-46v	Frontoparietal	Right Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Negative	-10.401	10.401	-11.493	-11.627	-11.764	-6.719
10	Left Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Right Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-10.400	10.400	-9.673	-13.521	-9.459	-8.947
11	Left Inferior Frontal Junction Posterior	Frontoparietal	Right Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-10.225	10.225	-10.738	-14.082	-8.342	-7.740
12	Left Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Right Lateral Intraparietal Dorsal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-10.135	10.135	-11.278	-14.414	-6.486	-8.361

13	Left Visual Area 3B	Visual2	Right Medial Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-9.994	9.994	-9.370	-12.672	-7.860	-10.074
14	Left Medial Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Right Medial Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-9.877	9.877	-10.666	-11.581	-9.439	-7.822
15	Right Visual Area 3B	Visual2	Right Medial Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-9.859	9.859	-10.445	-11.568	-6.455	-10.970
16	Right Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Right Area 7 Posterior Medial	Frontoparietal	Negative	-9.844	9.844	-9.363	-12.643	-11.731	-5.638
17	Left Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Left Area 7 Posterior Medial	Frontoparietal	Negative	-9.842	9.842	-9.417	-11.389	-11.387	-7.174
18	Left Inferior Frontal Junction Posterior	Frontoparietal	Left Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-9.657	9.657	-11.070	-13.096	-6.393	-8.066
19	Left Medial Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Left Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-9.608	9.608	-10.237	-11.722	-8.286	-8.186
20	Left Lateral Intraparietal Dorsal	Dorsal-attention	Right Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-9.537	9.537	-11.308	-11.939	-8.546	-6.356
21	Left Area 7 Posterior Medial	Frontoparietal	Right Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Negative	-9.434	9.434	-8.424	-11.104	-10.716	-7.492
22	Left Lateral Intraparietal Dorsal	Dorsal-attention	Left Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-9.427	9.427	-11.639	-11.990	-7.874	-6.205
23	Left Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Left Intraparietal 2	Frontoparietal	Negative	-9.299	9.299	-10.767	-9.544	-10.814	-6.069
24	Right Medial Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Right Visual Area 3CD	Visual2	Negative	-9.278	9.278	-10.232	-12.424	-7.193	-7.264
25	Left Anterior Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Right Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-9.267	9.267	-9.631	-10.760	-9.989	-6.688
26	Left Visual Area 3CD	Visual2	Right Medial Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-9.196	9.196	-11.120	-11.497	-7.015	-7.150
27	Left Visual Area 3B	Visual2	Left Inferior Frontal Junction Posterior	Frontoparietal	Negative	-9.012	9.012	-11.133	-8.772	-7.356	-8.785
28	Left Anterior Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Right Visual Area 3B	Visual2	Negative	-8.969	8.969	-8.936	-10.605	-7.398	-8.936
29	Left Intraparietal Sulcus 1	Visual2	Right Medial Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-8.947	8.947	-10.368	-10.354	-6.184	-8.881
30	Left Lateral Intraparietal Dorsal	Dorsal-attention	Right Visual Area 3B	Visual2	Negative	-8.934	8.934	-9.184	-11.490	-7.587	-7.476

31	Right Visual Area 3B	Visual2	Right Anterior Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-8.932	8.932	-10.485	-10.800	-6.254	-8.191
32	Left Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Left Area a9-46v	Frontoparietal	Negative	-8.844	8.844	-9.714	-9.106	-9.138	-7.416
33	Left Area p9-46v	Frontoparietal	Right Visual Area 3B	Visual2	Negative	-8.785	8.785	-10.060	-9.643	-8.460	-6.975
34	Left Medial Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Left Lateral Intraparietal Dorsal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-8.744	8.744	-9.403	-11.605	-7.819	-6.150
35	Left Intraparietal 2	Frontoparietal	Right Visual Area 3B	Visual2	Negative	-8.731	8.731	-9.453	-11.075	-7.575	-6.819
36	Left Area p9-46v	Frontoparietal	Right Dorsal Visual Temporal	Visual1	Negative	-8.599	8.599	-9.544	-11.517	-6.415	-6.920
37	Left Anterior Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Left Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-8.548	8.548	-10.687	-8.741	-7.011	-7.754
38	Left Intraparietal Sulcus 1	Visual2	Left Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-8.548	8.548	-9.687	-9.206	-6.679	-8.622
39	Left Inferior Frontal Junction Posterior	Frontoparietal	Right Lateral Intraparietal Dorsal	Dorsal-attention	Negative	-8.546	8.546	-8.369	-11.942	-6.109	-7.764
40	Right Visual Area 3B	Visual2	Right Intraparietal 2	Frontoparietal	Negative	-8.544	8.544	-8.898	-13.626	-5.750	-5.902
41	Left Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Right Intraparietal Sulcus 1	Visual2	Negative	-8.536	8.536	-8.677	-9.771	-6.261	-9.435
42	Left Intraparietal 0	Dorsal-attention	Right Visual Area 3B	Visual2	Negative	-8.529	8.529	-6.675	-8.170	-8.593	-10.679
43	Left Intraparietal Sulcus 1	Visual2	Left Inferior Frontal Junction Posterior	Frontoparietal	Negative	-8.503	8.503	-8.713	-11.691	-6.149	-7.458
44	Left Visual Area 3CD	Visual2	Right Intraparietal Sulcus 1	Visual2	Negative	-8.459	8.459	-7.186	-10.186	-6.784	-9.679
45	Left Lateral Intraparietal Dorsal	Dorsal-attention	Right Visual Area 3CD	Visual2	Negative	-8.457	8.457	-9.972	-11.654	-6.295	-5.906
46	Left Lateral Intraparietal Dorsal	Dorsal-attention	Right Primary Visual Cortex	Visual1	Negative	-8.455	8.455	-11.129	-7.245	-9.394	-6.051
47	Left Medial Intraparietal	Dorsal-attention	Left Parahippocampal	Visual2	Negative	-8.440	8.440	-9.473	-8.080	-6.234	-9.972
48	Right Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	Frontoparietal	Right Area a9-46v	Frontoparietal	Negative	-8.434	8.434	-7.436	-8.405	-7.583	-10.310
49	Left Visual Area 3B	Visual2	Left Area p9-46v	Frontoparietal	Negative	-8.431	8.431	-10.638	-8.589	-7.985	-6.512

50	Left Inferior Frontal Junction Posterior	Frontoparietal	Left Visual Area 3CD	Visual2	Negative	-8.423	8.423	-10.276	-9.449	-7.485	-6.483
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Table 5: Top 50 shared functional network connections.

1.f. Supplementary Table S6

short_label	full_label	original_label	network	hemisphere
L-thalamus	Left Thalamus	thalamus_left	Subcortical	L
L-putamen	Left Putamen	putamen_left	Subcortical	L
L-pallidum	Left Pallidum	pallidum_left	Subcortical	L
L-hippocampus	Left Hippocampus	hippocampus_left	Subcortical	L
L-diencephalon	diencephalon_left	diencephalon_left	Subcortical	L
L-cerebellum	Left Cerebellum	cerebellum_left	Subcortical	L
L-caudate	Left Caudate	caudate_left	Subcortical	L
L-amygdala	Left Amygdala	amygdala_left	Subcortical	L
L-accumbens	Left Accumbens	accumbens_left	Subcortical	L
L_pOFC	Left Posterior Orbitofrontal Cortex	L_pOFC	Orbito-Affective	L
L_Pir	Left Piriform	L_Pir	Orbito-Affective	L
L_AAIC	Left Anterior Agranular Insula	L_AAIC	Orbito-Affective	L
L_TPOJ3	Left Temporo-Parietal Junction 3	L_TPOJ3	Posterior-Multimodal	L
L_TPOJ2	Left Temporo-Parietal Junction 2	L_TPOJ2	Posterior-Multimodal	L
L_PCV	Left Posterior Cingulate Ventral	L_PCV	Posterior-Multimodal	L
L_v23ab	Left Area 23 Ventral	L_v23ab	Default	L
L_s32	Left Superior Area 32	L_s32	Default	L
L_p32	Left Posterior Area 32	L_p32	Default	L
L_d32	Left Dorsal Area 32	L_d32	Default	L
L_d23ab	Left Area 23 Dorsal	L_d23ab	Default	L
L_a24	Left Anterior Cingulate 24	L_a24	Default	L
L_TGd	Left Temporal Gyrus Dorsal	L_TGd	Default	L
L_TE2a	Left Temporal Area 2a	L_TE2a	Default	L
L_TE1m	Left Temporal Area 1m	L_TE1m	Default	L
L_TE1a	Left Temporal Area 1a	L_TE1a	Default	L
L_STSvp	Left Superior Temporal Sulcus Ventral Posterior	L_STSvp	Default	L
L_STSva	Left Superior Temporal Sulcus Ventral Anterior	L_STSva	Default	L
L_PreS	Left Presubiculum	L_PreS	Default	L
L_POS1	Left Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 1	L_POS1	Default	L
L_PHA2	Left Parahippocampal 2	L_PHA2	Default	L
L_PHA1	Left Parahippocampal 1	L_PHA1	Default	L
L_PGs	Left Posterior Gyrus Superior	L_PGs	Default	L
L_PGi	Left Posterior Gyrus Inferior	L_PGi	Default	L
L_OFC	Left Orbitofrontal Cortex	L_OFC	Default	L
L_H	Left Hippocampus	L_H	Default	L
L_EC	Left Entorhinal Cortex	L_EC	Default	L

L_9p	Left Area 9 Posterior	L_9p	Default	L
L_9m	Left Area 9 Medial	L_9m	Default	L
L_9a	Left Area 9a	L_9a	Default	L
L_8BL	Left Area 8B Lateral	L_8BL	Default	L
L_8Av	Left Area 8A Ventral	L_8Av	Default	L
L_8Ad	Left Area 8A Dorsal	L_8Ad	Default	L
L_7m	Left Area 7 Medial	L_7m	Default	L
L_47s	Left Area 47 Superior	L_47s	Default	L
L_47m	L_47m	L_47m	Default	L
L_47l	Left Area 47 Lateral	L_47l	Default	L
L_31pv	Left Area 31 Posterior Ventral	L_31pv	Default	L
L_31pd	Left Area 31 Posterior Dorsal	L_31pd	Default	L
L_31a	Left Area 31 Anterior	L_31a	Default	L
L_25	Left Area 25 (Subgenual)	L_25	Default	L
L_23d	Left Area 23 Dorsal	L_23d	Default	L
L_10v	Left Area 10 Ventral	L_10v	Default	L
L_10r	Left Area 10 Rostral	L_10r	Default	L
L_10pp	Left Area 10 Posterior Pole	L_10pp	Default	L
L_10d	Left Area 10 Dorsal	L_10d	Default	L
L_s6-8	L_s6-8	L_s6-8	Frontoparietal	L
L_p9-46v	L_p9-46v	L_p9-46v	Frontoparietal	L
L_p47r	Left Area p47r	L_p47r	Frontoparietal	L
L_p10p	Left Area p10p	L_p10p	Frontoparietal	L
L_i6-8	L_i6-8	L_i6-8	Frontoparietal	L
L_a9-46v	L_a9-46v	L_a9-46v	Frontoparietal	L
L_a47r	Left Area 47 Right	L_a47r	Frontoparietal	L
L_a10p	Left Area a10p	L_a10p	Frontoparietal	L
L_TE1p	Left Temporal Area 1p	L_TE1p	Frontoparietal	L
L_RSC	L_RSC	L_RSC	Frontoparietal	L
L_POS2	Left Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	L_POS2	Frontoparietal	L
L_PFm	Left Prefrontal Medial	L_PFm	Frontoparietal	L
L_IP2	Left Intraparietal 2	L_IP2	Frontoparietal	L
L_IP1	Left Intraparietal 1	L_IP1	Frontoparietal	L
L_IFSa	Left Inferior Frontal Sulcus Anterior	L_IFSa	Frontoparietal	L
L_IFJp	Left Inferior Frontal Junction Posterior	L_IFJp	Frontoparietal	L
L_AVI	Left Anterior Ventral Insula	L_AVI	Frontoparietal	L
L_8C	Left Area 8C	L_8C	Frontoparietal	L
L_8BM	Left Area 8BM	L_8BM	Frontoparietal	L
L_7Pm	Left Area 7 Posterior Medial	L_7Pm	Frontoparietal	L
L_13l	Left Area 13 Lateral (Insula)	L_13l	Frontoparietal	L
L_11l	Left Area 11 Lateral	L_11l	Frontoparietal	L
L_TPOJ1	Left Temporo-Parietal Junction 1	L_TPOJ1	Language	L
L_TGv	Left Temporal Gyrus Ventral	L_TGv	Language	L
L_STV	Left Superior Temporal Ventral	L_STV	Language	L

L_STSdp	Left Superior Temporal Sulcus Dorsal Posterior	L_STSdp	Language	L
L_STSda	Left Superior Temporal Sulcus Dorsal Anterior	L_STSda	Language	L
L_STGa	Left Superior Temporal Gyrus Anterior	L_STGa	Language	L
L_SFL	Left Superior Frontal Lobule	L_SFL	Language	L
L_PSL	Left Parietal Superior Lobule	L_PSL	Language	L
L_IFSp	Left Inferior Frontal Sulcus Posterior	L_IFSp	Language	L
L_IFJa	Left Inferior Frontal Junction Anterior	L_IFJa	Language	L
L_A5	Left Auditory Area 5	L_A5	Language	L
L_55b	Left Area 55b	L_55b	Language	L
L_45	Left Area 45 (Broca)	L_45	Language	L
L_44	Left Area 44 (Broca)	L_44	Language	L
L_p32pr	Left Posterior Area 32pr	L_p32pr	Cingulo-Opercular	L
L_p24pr	Left Posterior Cingulate 24pr	L_p24pr	Cingulo-Opercular	L
L_p24	Left Posterior Cingulate 24	L_p24	Cingulo-Opercular	L
L_a32pr	L_a32pr	L_a32pr	Cingulo-Opercular	L
L_a24pr	Left Anterior Cingulate 24pr	L_a24pr	Cingulo-Opercular	L
L_SCEF	Left Supplementary Cingulate Eye Field	L_SCEF	Cingulo-Opercular	L
L_PoI2	Left Postcentral Insula 2	L_PoI2	Cingulo-Opercular	L
L_PoI1	Left Postcentral Insula 1	L_PoI1	Cingulo-Opercular	L
L_PI	Left Posterior Insula	L_PI	Cingulo-Opercular	L
L_PFop	Left Prefrontal Opercular	L_PFop	Cingulo-Opercular	L
L_PFcm	Left Prefrontal Cortex Medial	L_PFcm	Cingulo-Opercular	L
L_PF	Left Prefrontal	L_PF	Cingulo-Opercular	L
L_MI	Left Motor Insula	L_MI	Cingulo-Opercular	L
L_FOP5	Left Frontal Opercular 5	L_FOP5	Cingulo-Opercular	L
L_FOP4	Left Frontal Opercular 4	L_FOP4	Cingulo-Opercular	L
L_FOP3	Left Frontal Opercular 3	L_FOP3	Cingulo-Opercular	L
L_FOP1	Left Frontal Opercular 1	L_FOP1	Cingulo-Opercular	L
L_FEF	Left Frontal Eye Field	L_FEF	Cingulo-Opercular	L
L_9-46d	L_9-46d	L_9-46d	Cingulo-Opercular	L
L_7Am	Left Area 7 Medial	L_7Am	Cingulo-Opercular	L
L_6r	Left Premotor 6r	L_6r	Cingulo-Opercular	L
L_6ma	Left Area 6ma	L_6ma	Cingulo-Opercular	L
L_5mv	Left Area 5 Medial Ventral	L_5mv	Cingulo-Opercular	L
L_46	Left Area 46 (Dorsolateral Prefrontal)	L_46	Cingulo-Opercular	L
L_43	Left Area 43	L_43	Cingulo-Opercular	L
L_33pr	Left Area 33pr	L_33pr	Cingulo-Opercular	L
L_23c	Left Area 23c	L_23c	Cingulo-Opercular	L
L_TF	Left Temporal Fusiform	L_TF	Ventral-Multimodal	L
L_PeEc	Left Perirhinal Entorhinal Cortex	L_PeEc	Ventral-Multimodal	L
L_TE2p	Left Temporal Area 2p	L_TE2p	Dorsal-attention	L
L_PHT	Left Parahippocampal Temporal	L_PHT	Dorsal-attention	L
L_PHA3	Left Parahippocampal 3	L_PHA3	Dorsal-attention	L
L_PGp	Left Posterior Gyrus Parietal	L_PGp	Dorsal-attention	L

L_PFt	Left Prefrontal Temporal	L_PFt	Dorsal-attention	L
L_PEF	Left Parietal Eye Field	L_PEF	Dorsal-attention	L
L_MIP	Left Medial Intraparietal	L_MIP	Dorsal-attention	L
L_LIPd	Left Lateral Intraparietal Dorsal	L_LIPd	Dorsal-attention	L
L_IP0	Left Intraparietal 0	L_IP0	Dorsal-attention	L
L_AIP	Left Anterior Intraparietal	L_AIP	Dorsal-attention	L
L_7PL	Left Area 7 Parietal Lobule	L_7PL	Dorsal-attention	L
L_6a	Left Premotor 6a	L_6a	Dorsal-attention	L
L_TA2	Left Temporal Area 2	L_TA2	Auditory	L
L_RI	L_RI	L_RI	Auditory	L
L_PBelt	Left Posterior Belt	L_PBelt	Auditory	L
L_MBelt	Left Medial Belt	L_MBelt	Auditory	L
L_LBelt	Left Lateral Belt	L_LBelt	Auditory	L
L_A4	Left Auditory Area 4	L_A4	Auditory	L
L_A1	Left Primary Auditory Cortex	L_A1	Auditory	L
L_52	Left Area 52	L_52	Auditory	L
L_OP4	Left Opercular 4	L_OP4	Somatomotor	L
L_OP2-3	L_OP2-3	L_OP2-3	Somatomotor	L
L_OP1	Left Opercular 1	L_OP1	Somatomotor	L
L_Ig	Left Granular Insula	L_Ig	Somatomotor	L
L_FOP2	Left Frontal Opercular 2	L_FOP2	Somatomotor	L
L_7PC	Left Area 7 Parietal Convexity	L_7PC	Somatomotor	L
L_7AL	Left Area 7 Anterior Lobule	L_7AL	Somatomotor	L
L_6v	Left Premotor 6v	L_6v	Somatomotor	L
L_6mp	Left Premotor 6mp	L_6mp	Somatomotor	L
L_6d	Left Premotor 6d	L_6d	Somatomotor	L
L_5m	Left Area 5 Medial	L_5m	Somatomotor	L
L_5L	Left Area 5 Lateral	L_5L	Somatomotor	L
L_4	Left Primary Motor Cortex	L_4	Somatomotor	L
L_3b	Left Somatosensory 3b	L_3b	Somatomotor	L
L_3a	Left Somatosensory 3a	L_3a	Somatomotor	L
L_24dv	Left Anterior Cingulate 24dv	L_24dv	Somatomotor	L
L_24dd	Left Anterior Cingulate 24dd	L_24dd	Somatomotor	L
L_2	Left Secondary Somatosensory	L_2	Somatomotor	L
L_1	Left Primary Somatosensory	L_1	Somatomotor	L
L_VVC	Left Ventral Visual Complex	L_VVC	Visual2	L
L_VMV3	Left Ventromedial V3	L_VMV3	Visual2	L
L_VMV2	Left Ventromedial V2	L_VMV2	Visual2	L
L_VMV1	Left Ventromedial V1	L_VMV1	Visual2	L
L_VIP	Left Ventral Intraparietal	L_VIP	Visual2	L
L_V8	Left Visual Area 8	L_V8	Visual2	L
L_V7	Left Visual Area 7	L_V7	Visual2	L
L_V6A	Left Visual Area 6A	L_V6A	Visual2	L
L_V6	Left Visual Area 6	L_V6	Visual2	L

L_V4t	Left Visual Area 4 Transitional	L_V4t	Visual2	L
L_V4	Left Visual Area 4	L_V4	Visual2	L
L_V3CD	Left Visual Area 3CD	L_V3CD	Visual2	L
L_V3B	Left Visual Area 3B	L_V3B	Visual2	L
L_V3A	Left Visual Area 3A	L_V3A	Visual2	L
L_V3	Left Visual Area 3	L_V3	Visual2	L
L_V2	Left Secondary Visual Cortex	L_V2	Visual2	L
L_PIT	Left Posterior Inferotemporal	L_PIT	Visual2	L
L_PH	Left Parahippocampal	L_PH	Visual2	L
L_MT	Left Middle Temporal	L_MT	Visual2	L
L_MST	Left Medial Superior Temporal	L_MST	Visual2	L
L_LO3	Left Lateral Occipital 3	L_LO3	Visual2	L
L_LO2	Left Lateral Occipital 2	L_LO2	Visual2	L
L_LO1	Left Lateral Occipital 1	L_LO1	Visual2	L
L_LIPv	Left Lateral Intraparietal Ventral	L_LIPv	Visual2	L
L_IPS1	Left Intraparietal Sulcus 1	L_IPS1	Visual2	L
L_FST	Left Fundus of Superior Temporal	L_FST	Visual2	L
L_FFC	Left Fusiform Face Complex	L_FFC	Visual2	L
L_V1	Left Primary Visual Cortex	L_V1	Visual1	L
L_ProS	Left Prosubiculum	L_ProS	Visual1	L
L_DVT	Left Dorsal Visual Temporal	L_DVT	Visual1	L
R_DVT	Right Dorsal Visual Temporal	R_DVT	Visual1	R
R_ProS	Right Prosubiculum	R_ProS	Visual1	R
R_V1	Right Primary Visual Cortex	R_V1	Visual1	R
R_FFC	Right Fusiform Face Complex	R_FFC	Visual2	R
R_FST	Right Fundus of Superior Temporal	R_FST	Visual2	R
R_IPS1	Right Intraparietal Sulcus 1	R_IPS1	Visual2	R
R_LIPv	Right Lateral Intraparietal Ventral	R_LIPv	Visual2	R
R_LO1	Right Lateral Occipital 1	R_LO1	Visual2	R
R_LO2	Right Lateral Occipital 2	R_LO2	Visual2	R
R_LO3	Right Lateral Occipital 3	R_LO3	Visual2	R
R_MST	Right Medial Superior Temporal	R_MST	Visual2	R
R_MT	Right Middle Temporal	R_MT	Visual2	R
R_PH	Right Parahippocampal	R_PH	Visual2	R
R_PIT	Right Posterior Inferotemporal	R_PIT	Visual2	R
R_V2	Right Secondary Visual Cortex	R_V2	Visual2	R
R_V3	Right Visual Area 3	R_V3	Visual2	R
R_V3A	Right Visual Area 3A	R_V3A	Visual2	R
R_V3B	Right Visual Area 3B	R_V3B	Visual2	R
R_V3CD	Right Visual Area 3CD	R_V3CD	Visual2	R
R_V4	Right Visual Area 4	R_V4	Visual2	R
R_V4t	Right Visual Area 4 Transitional	R_V4t	Visual2	R
R_V6	Right Visual Area 6	R_V6	Visual2	R
R_V6A	Right Visual Area 6A	R_V6A	Visual2	R

R_V7	Right Visual Area 7	R_V7	Visual2	R
R_V8	Right Visual Area 8	R_V8	Visual2	R
R_VIP	Right Ventral Intraparietal	R_VIP	Visual2	R
R_VMV1	Right Ventromedial V1	R_VMV1	Visual2	R
R_VMV2	Right Ventromedial V2	R_VMV2	Visual2	R
R_VMV3	Right Ventromedial V3	R_VMV3	Visual2	R
R_VVC	Right Ventral Visual Complex	R_VVC	Visual2	R
R_1	Right Primary Somatosensory	R_1	Somatomotor	R
R_2	Right Secondary Somatosensory	R_2	Somatomotor	R
R_24dd	Right Anterior Cingulate 24dd	R_24dd	Somatomotor	R
R_24dv	Right Anterior Cingulate 24dv	R_24dv	Somatomotor	R
R_3a	Right Somatosensory 3a	R_3a	Somatomotor	R
R_3b	Right Somatosensory 3b	R_3b	Somatomotor	R
R_4	Right Primary Motor Cortex	R_4	Somatomotor	R
R_5L	Right Area 5 Lateral	R_5L	Somatomotor	R
R_5m	Right Area 5 Medial	R_5m	Somatomotor	R
R_6d	Right Premotor 6d	R_6d	Somatomotor	R
R_6mp	Right Premotor 6mp	R_6mp	Somatomotor	R
R_6v	Right Premotor 6v	R_6v	Somatomotor	R
R_7AL	Right Area 7 Anterior Lobule	R_7AL	Somatomotor	R
R_7PC	Right Area 7 Parietal Convexity	R_7PC	Somatomotor	R
R_FOP2	Right Frontal Opercular 2	R_FOP2	Somatomotor	R
R_Ig	Right Granular Insula	R_Ig	Somatomotor	R
R_OP1	Right Opercular 1	R_OP1	Somatomotor	R
R_OP2-3	R_OP2-3	R_OP2-3	Somatomotor	R
R_OP4	Right Opercular 4	R_OP4	Somatomotor	R
R_RI	Right Retroinsular	R_RI	Somatomotor	R
R_52	Right Area 52	R_52	Auditory	R
R_A1	Right Primary Auditory Cortex	R_A1	Auditory	R
R_A4	Right Auditory Area 4	R_A4	Auditory	R
R_LBelt	Right Lateral Belt	R_LBelt	Auditory	R
R_MBelt	Right Medial Belt	R_MBelt	Auditory	R
R_PBelt	Right Posterior Belt	R_PBelt	Auditory	R
R_TA2	Right Temporal Area 2	R_TA2	Auditory	R
R_6a	Right Premotor 6a	R_6a	Dorsal-attention	R
R_7PL	Right Area 7 Parietal Lobule	R_7PL	Dorsal-attention	R
R_AIP	Right Anterior Intraparietal	R_AIP	Dorsal-attention	R
R_IP0	Right Intraparietal 0	R_IP0	Dorsal-attention	R
R_LIPd	Right Lateral Intraparietal Dorsal	R_LIPd	Dorsal-attention	R
R_MIP	Right Medial Intraparietal	R_MIP	Dorsal-attention	R
R_PFt	Right Prefrontal Temporal	R_PFt	Dorsal-attention	R
R_PGp	Right Posterior Gyrus Parietal	R_PGp	Dorsal-attention	R
R_PHA3	Right Parahippocampal 3	R_PHA3	Dorsal-attention	R
R_PHT	Right Parahippocampal Temporal	R_PHT	Dorsal-attention	R

R_TE2p	Right Temporal Area 2p	R_TE2p	Dorsal-attention	R
R_PeEc	Right Perirhinal Entorhinal Cortex	R_PeEc	Ventral-Multimodal	R
R_TF	Right Temporal Fusiform	R_TF	Ventral-Multimodal	R
R_23c	Right Area 23c	R_23c	Cingulo-Opercular	R
R_43	Right Area 43	R_43	Cingulo-Opercular	R
R_46	Right Area 46 (Dorsolateral Prefrontal)	R_46	Cingulo-Opercular	R
R_5mv	Right Area 5 Medial Ventral	R_5mv	Cingulo-Opercular	R
R_6ma	Right Area 6ma	R_6ma	Cingulo-Opercular	R
R_6r	Right Premotor 6r	R_6r	Cingulo-Opercular	R
R_7Am	Right Area 7 Medial	R_7Am	Cingulo-Opercular	R
R_9-46d	R_9-46d	R_9-46d	Cingulo-Opercular	R
R_FEF	Right Frontal Eye Field	R_FEF	Cingulo-Opercular	R
R_FOP1	Right Frontal Opercular 1	R_FOP1	Cingulo-Opercular	R
R_FOP3	Right Frontal Opercular 3	R_FOP3	Cingulo-Opercular	R
R_FOP4	Right Frontal Opercular 4	R_FOP4	Cingulo-Opercular	R
R_FOP5	Right Frontal Opercular 5	R_FOP5	Cingulo-Opercular	R
R_IFSa	Right Inferior Frontal Sulcus Anterior	R_IFSa	Cingulo-Opercular	R
R_MI	Right Motor Insula	R_MI	Cingulo-Opercular	R
R_PEF	Right Parietal Eye Field	R_PEF	Cingulo-Opercular	R
R_PF	Right Prefrontal	R_PF	Cingulo-Opercular	R
R_PFcm	Right Prefrontal Cortex Medial	R_PFcm	Cingulo-Opercular	R
R_PFop	Right Prefrontal Opercular	R_PFop	Cingulo-Opercular	R
R_PI	Right Posterior Insula	R_PI	Cingulo-Opercular	R
R_PSL	Right Parietal Superior Lobule	R_PSL	Cingulo-Opercular	R
R_PoI1	Right Postcentral Insula 1	R_PoI1	Cingulo-Opercular	R
R_PoI2	Right Postcentral Insula 2	R_PoI2	Cingulo-Opercular	R
R_SCEF	Right Supplementary Cingulate Eye Field	R_SCEF	Cingulo-Opercular	R
R_a24pr	Right Anterior Cingulate 24pr	R_a24pr	Cingulo-Opercular	R
R_a32pr	R_a32pr	R_a32pr	Cingulo-Opercular	R
R_p24	Right Posterior Cingulate 24	R_p24	Cingulo-Opercular	R
R_p24pr	Right Posterior Cingulate 24pr	R_p24pr	Cingulo-Opercular	R
R_p32pr	Right Posterior Area 32pr	R_p32pr	Cingulo-Opercular	R
R_45	Right Area 45 (Broca)	R_45	Language	R
R_55b	Right Area 55b	R_55b	Language	R
R_A5	Right Auditory Area 5	R_A5	Language	R
R_IFJa	Right Inferior Frontal Junction Anterior	R_IFJa	Language	R
R_SFL	Right Superior Frontal Lobule	R_SFL	Language	R
R_STGa	Right Superior Temporal Gyrus Anterior	R_STGa	Language	R
R_STSdp	Right Superior Temporal Sulcus Dorsal Posterior	R_STSdp	Language	R
R_TGv	Right Temporal Gyrus Ventral	R_TGv	Language	R
R_TPOJ1	Right Temporo-Parietal Junction 1	R_TPOJ1	Language	R
R_11l	Right Area 11 Lateral	R_11l	Frontoparietal	R
R_13l	Right Area 13 Lateral (Insula)	R_13l	Frontoparietal	R
R_31a	Right Area 31 Anterior	R_31a	Frontoparietal	R

R_33pr	Right Area 33pr	R_33pr	Frontoparietal	R
R_44	Right Area 44 (Broca)	R_44	Frontoparietal	R
R_7Pm	Right Area 7 Posterior Medial	R_7Pm	Frontoparietal	R
R_8BM	Right Area 8BM	R_8BM	Frontoparietal	R
R_8C	Right Area 8C	R_8C	Frontoparietal	R
R_AVI	Right Anterior Ventral Insula	R_AVI	Frontoparietal	R
R_IFJp	Right Inferior Frontal Junction Posterior	R_IFJp	Frontoparietal	R
R_IFSp	Right Inferior Frontal Sulcus Posterior	R_IFSp	Frontoparietal	R
R_IP1	Right Intraparietal 1	R_IP1	Frontoparietal	R
R_IP2	Right Intraparietal 2	R_IP2	Frontoparietal	R
R_OFC	Right Orbitofrontal Cortex	R_OFC	Frontoparietal	R
R_PFm	Right Prefrontal Medial	R_PFm	Frontoparietal	R
R_POS2	Right Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 2	R_POS2	Frontoparietal	R
R_RSC	Right Retrosplenial Cortex	R_RSC	Frontoparietal	R
R_TE1m	Right Temporal Area 1m	R_TE1m	Frontoparietal	R
R_TE1p	Right Temporal Area 1p	R_TE1p	Frontoparietal	R
R_a10p	Right Area a10p	R_a10p	Frontoparietal	R
R_a47r	Right Area 47 Right	R_a47r	Frontoparietal	R
R_a9-46v	R_a9-46v	R_a9-46v	Frontoparietal	R
R_d32	Right Dorsal Area 32	R_d32	Frontoparietal	R
R_i6-8	R_i6-8	R_i6-8	Frontoparietal	R
R_p10p	Right Area p10p	R_p10p	Frontoparietal	R
R_p47r	Right Area p47r	R_p47r	Frontoparietal	R
R_p9-46v	R_p9-46v	R_p9-46v	Frontoparietal	R
R_s6-8	R_s6-8	R_s6-8	Frontoparietal	R
R_10d	Right Area 10 Dorsal	R_10d	Default	R
R_10pp	Right Area 10 Posterior Pole	R_10pp	Default	R
R_10r	Right Area 10 Rostral	R_10r	Default	R
R_10v	Right Area 10 Ventral	R_10v	Default	R
R_23d	Right Area 23 Dorsal	R_23d	Default	R
R_25	Right Area 25 (Subgenual)	R_25	Default	R
R_31pd	Right Area 31 Posterior Dorsal	R_31pd	Default	R
R_31pv	Right Area 31 Posterior Ventral	R_31pv	Default	R
R_47l	Right Area 47 Lateral	R_47l	Default	R
R_47m	R_47m	R_47m	Default	R
R_47s	Right Area 47 Superior	R_47s	Default	R
R_7m	Right Area 7 Medial	R_7m	Default	R
R_8Ad	Right Area 8A Dorsal	R_8Ad	Default	R
R_8Av	Right Area 8A Ventral	R_8Av	Default	R
R_8BL	Right Area 8B Lateral	R_8BL	Default	R
R_9a	Right Area 9a	R_9a	Default	R
R_9m	Right Area 9 Medial	R_9m	Default	R
R_9p	Right Area 9 Posterior	R_9p	Default	R
R_EC	Right Entorhinal Cortex	R_EC	Default	R

R_H	Right Hippocampus	R_H	Default	R
R_PGi	Right Posterior Gyrus Inferior	R_PGi	Default	R
R_PGs	Right Posterior Gyrus Superior	R_PGs	Default	R
R_PHA1	Right Parahippocampal 1	R_PHA1	Default	R
R_PHA2	Right Parahippocampal 2	R_PHA2	Default	R
R_POS1	Right Parieto-Occipital Sulcus 1	R_POS1	Default	R
R_PreS	Right Presubiculum	R_PreS	Default	R
R_STSda	Right Superior Temporal Sulcus Dorsal Anterior	R_STSda	Default	R
R_STSva	Right Superior Temporal Sulcus Ventral Anterior	R_STSva	Default	R
R_STSvp	Right Superior Temporal Sulcus Ventral Posterior	R_STSvp	Default	R
R_TE1a	Right Temporal Area 1a	R_TE1a	Default	R
R_TE2a	Right Temporal Area 2a	R_TE2a	Default	R
R_TGd	Right Temporal Gyrus Dorsal	R_TGd	Default	R
R_a24	Right Anterior Cingulate 24	R_a24	Default	R
R_d23ab	Right Area 23 Dorsal	R_d23ab	Default	R
R_p32	Right Posterior Area 32	R_p32	Default	R
R_s32	Right Superior Area 32	R_s32	Default	R
R_v23ab	Right Area 23 Ventral	R_v23ab	Default	R
R_PCV	Right Posterior Cingulate Ventral	R_PCV	Posterior-Multimodal	R
R_STV	Right Superior Temporal Ventral	R_STV	Posterior-Multimodal	R
R_TPOJ2	Right Temporo-Parietal Junction 2	R_TPOJ2	Posterior-Multimodal	R
R_TPOJ3	Right Temporo-Parietal Junction 3	R_TPOJ3	Posterior-Multimodal	R
R_AAIC	Right Anterior Agranular Insula	R_AAIC	Orbito-Affective	R
R_Pir	Right Piriform	R_Pir	Orbito-Affective	R
R_pOFC	Right Posterior Orbitofrontal Cortex	R_pOFC	Orbito-Affective	R
R-accumbens	Right Accumbens	accumbens_right	Subcortical	R
R-amygdala	Right Amygdala	amygdala_right	Subcortical	R
R-caudate	Right Caudate	caudate_right	Subcortical	R
R-cerebellum	Right Cerebellum	cerebellum_right	Subcortical	R
R-diencephalon	diencephalon_right	diencephalon_right	Subcortical	R
R-hippocampus	Right Hippocampus	hippocampus_right	Subcortical	R
R-pallidum	Right Pallidum	pallidum_right	Subcortical	R
R-putamen	Right Putamen	putamen_right	Subcortical	R
R-thalamus	Right Thalamus	thalamus_right	Subcortical	R

Table 6: Node labels and network assignments.

REFERENCES

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